

Geospatial Least Cost Electrification Planning – Study Case Sierra Leone

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1. Country Context

- This work takes into consideration the country's energy drive towards sustainable energy for all and the country's commitment to achieve universal access by 2030
- Pop in base year: 7,374,265
- Urban ratio: 42.1 % (57.9% is considered rural or peri-urban pop)
- Pop growth rate: 2.0%
- Pop in end year : 9,901,257
- Average HH size: 4.4 urban 5.2 rural
- National elec. rate*: 23.0%
- -Urban elec. Rate:49.0%
- -Rural elec. rate: 5.0%
- Electricity Access = 31%,
- Electricity Maximum Demand is 700MW

Sector Challenges & Targets

CHALLENGES

- Sierra Leone faces several challenges in increasing electricity access
- Poor and limited state of transmission and distribution networks
- Strong indications of unmet level of generating capacities to meet demand
- Fossil fuels pricing escalation cause thermal generation cost increase
- Very high cost to build new generation assets resulting in high cost of electricity

TARGETS (SL Govt, SE4ALL, INDC, SDG 7)

- Increase electricity access from 31% in 2022 to 80 % in 2030
- Increase in Installed generation capacity to 650 MW in 2030
- Increase of per capita electricity consumption from 13.3 kWh in 2017 to 26.3 kWh in 2030.

Research Question

How would Sierra Leone electricity supply pathways able to meets the policy demand by providing affordable, reliable and sustainable electricity for all by 2030 ?

2.Scenarios

Using the OnSSET tool, the following two scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Business Asusual	Electrification objective of government to ensure the economy has sustained growth	Assumed increased electrification rate to be consistent with the increase in the per capita income over the planning period.
Scenario 1	Generation expansion pathways	Supply to meet demand by increased participation of solar, whilst reducing influence of HFO and LFO to reduce emission.
Scenario 2	Effect of reducing of PV into the generation mix	Maintaining demand as given in scenario1 and reducing the intervention of solar PV by 25 %

BUSINESS AS USUAL

Total New Connections- Business as Usual

CONTD

CONTD

Total Capacity- Business as Usual

SCENARIO 1- NEW CONNECTIONS

New Connections- Scenario1

SCENARIO1-TOTAL CAPACITY

SCENARIO 1-TOTAL INVESTMENTS

Conclusions and Policy Insights

Conclusion

- Reduce dependence on fossil fuels import and more investment on renewable technologies
- Grid densification plays a crucial role in achieving the targeted electricity access target rate of 100% by 2030 with increase in the number of new connections
- The intervention of mini grid also increases the access rate

Policy Insights

- Improve energy security: by developing technologies that runs on locally available resources.
- Align energy sector transformation goals with SDG7 targets (e.g: Installed generation – 160MW in 2022 to 650MW in 2030, Renewable generation – 35% in 2022 to 80% in 2030, etc)

Future Work

- Optimal technology mix to achieve universal access
- Expected/targeted elec demand for different locations of settlements
- Geospatial extent of the roll out electrification plan

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